

The *acetyl* derivative melts at 280°. (Found: C, 63·7; H, 3·8; M. W., 300. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 64·0; H, 4·0 per cent. M. W., 298). 4-Hydroxy-3:4'-dicarboxydiphenyl was oxidised as before and terephthalic acid identified as its methyl ester.

2-Hydroxy-5:4'-dicarboxydiphenyl melts above 300°. (Found: C, 64·8; H, 3·5. $C_{14}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 65·1; H, 3·8 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative melts above 300°. (Found: C, 63·6; H, 3·6; M. W. 299. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 64·0; H, 4·0 per cent. M. W., 300).

2-Hydroxy-5:4'-dicarboxydiphenyl was oxidised as before and terephthalic acid identified as its methyl ester.

In conclusion the author desires to express his grateful thanks to Prof. P. C. Mitter for much encouragement and advice during the course of this work.

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Extension of Michael's Reaction. Part V.

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In Part IV (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 355) it has been shown that $\alpha\alpha'$ -phenylcarbonylacetone dicarboxylate which contains two active hydrogen atoms in 1:3-position reacts readily with benzaldehyde to yield a compound which, in all probability, possesses a tricyclic structure. A very notable feature of this compound is its remarkable stability towards acid and alkali in spite of its complex molecular structure. In this connection mention should be made of an analogous observation of Knoevenagel (*Annalen*, 1895, **288**, 347) which shows that benzylidenebisacetone dicarboxylic ester, obtained by condensing acetone dicarboxylic ester with benzaldehyde, reacts with another molecule of the aldehyde to yield the following ring-compound

The sodium derivative of ethyl acetone dicarboxylate reacts with α -naphthylisocyanate to give a piperidine compound (IV) instead of the open-chain dinaphthylcarbonyl derivative analogous to compound (I).

The compound (IV) reacts with aldehyde to yield a compound which can be represented by either of the two following formulæ (V) and (Va). The original compound (IV) has been found to give a

monosodium derivative, whereas the aldehyde compound does not form any sodium salt. In view of the fact that a compound containing the system $-\text{CO}-\text{CH}(\text{CO}_2\text{Et})-\text{CO}-$ as in the formula (Va) should be acidic in nature, the formula (Va) is rejected in preference to the bridged formula (V) in which enolisation cannot take place according to Bredt's law (*cf.* Ghosh and Guba, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 354).

The compound (IV) gets easily hydrolysed by alkali to yield the compound (VI). It was expected that the compound (VI), by reason of the presence of two active methylene groups, would react with two molecules of aldehyde; but it is, however, interesting to note that it reacts actually with one molecule of aldehyde to yield the bridged compound (VII), the constitution of which is confirmed by the fact that the aldehyde compound is insoluble in alkali.

(VI)

(VII)

Ethyl acetone dicarboxylate reacts with carbethoxythiocarbimide to give a thiopyran compound (VIII) according to the following scheme. The compound is not endowed with any mercaptanic property and cannot be desulphurised by oxide of mercury confirming thereby the presence of the sulphur atom as a member of the ring.

VIII

In part IV (*loc. cit.*, p. 354) it has been shown that, under all conditions, only one molecule of phenylthiocarbimide reacts with ethyl acetone dicarboxylate to yield a thiopyran compound, whereas in the above reaction carbethoxythiocarbimide attacks both the methylene groups of ethyl acetone dicarboxylate. The greater reactivity of carbethoxythiocarbimide can be explained on the basis that the carbethoxy group, which has much smaller affinity demand than phenyl, endows the unsaturated group C=S in thiocarbimide with more residual affinity and hence, greater additive power (*cf.* Ingold and Weaver, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 378; Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1933, 16A, 105). It follows, therefore, that naphthyl isocyanate, in which there are two fused benzene rings, should be less reactive than phenyl isocyanate, which is actually the case as is evinced by a comparison of the compounds (I and IV).

The disodium derivative of 2:6-diketo-4:4-dimethylcyclohexane-3:5-dicarboxylate does not react with phenyl isocyanate. It is significant to note that this fact is not singular but is observed amongst other homocyclic compounds, and that in all probability an important generalisation with regard to the inactivity of the sodium derivatives of homocyclic compounds in Michael's reaction is involved,

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl aa'-phenylcarbonylaceton dicarboxylate (I) was prepared according to the method of Ghosh and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 359).

Action of formaldehyde upon compound (I): *Formation of ethyl 2:4-diphenylcarbony-cyclobutanone-2:4-dicarboxylate* (II, R=H).—To a boiling acetic acid solution of the compound (I), excess of formaldehyde was added. The solution was heated under reflux for about 30 minutes, when on cooling a brown solid was obtained which crystallised from acetic acid in brownish white rectangular plates, m. p. 248° (decomp.). (Found: C, 63.38; H, 5.69; N, 6.17. $C_{24}H_{24}O_7N_2$ requires C, 63.72; H, 5.31; N, 6.19 per cent). It is soluble in alkali and precipitated by acids.

The *semicarbazone* was obtained in the usual manner and was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. above 270°.

Action of acetaldehyde upon compound (I): *Formation of ethyl 2:4-diphenylcarbony-3-methylcyclobutanone-2:4-dicarboxylate* (II, R=CH₃).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the above compound. The reddish brown product was purified by precipitation by acid from its solution in alkali and was finally crystallised from a mixture of acetic acid and alcohol in brownish white rectangular plates, m. p. 200-202° (decomp.). (Found: C, 64.01; H, 5.86. $C_{25}H_{26}O_7N_2$ requires C, 64.37; H, 5.58 per cent). It is soluble in alkali.

Action of salicylaldehyde methylether upon compound (I): *Formation of compound* [III, R=C₆H₄(OCH₃)].—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the previous compounds. The product was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in fine yellow rectangular plates, m. p. 205-206°. (Found: C, 69.27; H, 4.28. $C_{27}H_{18}O_6N_2$ requires C, 69.54; H, 3.86 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali.

Action of cinnamic aldehyde upon compound (I): *Formation of compound* (III, R=PhCH:CH).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the previous compounds. The product was crystallised from a large quantity of glacial acetic acid in fine orange needles, m. p. 249-50° (decomp.). (Found: C, 73.06; H, 3.58. $C_{28}H_{18}O_5N_2$ requires C, 72.73; H, 3.89 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali and sparingly soluble in alcohol.

Action of acetophenone upon compound (I).—An acetic anhydride solution of the equimolecular proportions of the compound (I) and

acetophenone was heated under reflux for about 2 hours, when on cooling and standing for sufficiently long time, a very small quantity of yellow crystalline solid was obtained. A part of the product was soluble in alkali and was precipitated by acids and crystallised from acetic acid in brownish white rectangular plates, m.p. 224-25° (decomp.). The alkali-insoluble portion crystallised from a large quantity of glacial acetic acid in light yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 303-304° (decomp.). The yield of both the compounds was too poor to allow any further studies. From the mother-liquor, however, only a tarry product was obtained by evaporation or dilution with water.

1-Naphthyl-3-carbethoxy-2 : 4 : 6-triketopiperidine (IV).—Sodium (2.3 g.) was gradually added to a solution of ethyl acetone dicarboxylate (10.2 g.) in absolute ether (200 c.c.). After the evolution of hydrogen had ceased, α -naphthyl isocyanate (8.5 g.) was added to the solution when the reaction commenced immediately. The precipitate was filtered overnight, dissolved in water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a solid separated which crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 191-92° (decomp.), yield 14 g. [Found: C, 66.22; H, 4.98; N, 4.16; M. W. (by titration), 325. $C_{18}H_{15}O_5N$ requires C, 66.46; H, 4.61; N, 4.31 per cent. M.W., 325]. It has been found by titration with standard caustic soda solution that it forms monosodium salt.

The same compound (IV) was obtained when α -naphthyl isocyanate (2 mols.) was allowed to react with ethyl acetone dicarboxylate (1 mol.).

1-Naphthyl-3-carbethoxy-3 : 5-cinnamylidene-2 : 4 : 6-triketopiperidine (V, R=PhCH:CH).—An acetic acid solution of equimolecular proportions of the compound (IV) and cinnamic aldehyde was heated under reflux for about an hour. On cooling, a crystalline precipitate soon separated which crystallised from acetic acid in beautiful orange plates, m. p. 236-37° (decomp.). (Found: C, 73.51; H, 5.17. $C_{27}H_{21}O_5N$ requires C, 73.80; H, 4.78 per cent). It is sparingly soluble in alcohol and insoluble in alkali.

1-Naphthyl-3-carbethoxy-3 : 5-o-nitrobenzylidene-2 : 4 : 6-triketopiperidine (V, R=*o*-nitrophenyl).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the above compound. The product crystallised from glacial acetic acid in reddish brown rectangular plates, m. p. above 300°. (Found: N, 6.32. $C_{25}H_{18}O_7N_2$ requires N, 6.11 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali.

Hydrolysis of compound (IV): Formation of 1-naphthyl-2 : 4 : 6-triketopiperidine (VI).—The above compound (IV) (10 g.) was heated

under reflux with alcoholic potash (15%) for about 8 hours and the alcohol was then distilled under reduced pressure. The solid was treated with water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when there was evolution of carbon dioxide. The solid thus obtained crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 249-50° (decomp.), yield 5.5 g. It is insoluble in aqueous bicarbonate solution but readily soluble in alkali. (Found: C, 70.93; H, 4.68; N, 5.51. $C_{15}H_{11}O_3N$ requires C, 71.14; H, 4.34; N, 5.53 per cent).

1-Naphthyl-3:5-*o*-nitrobenzylidene-2:4:6-triketopiperidine (VII, R=*o*-nitrophenyl).—An acetic acid solution of equimolecular proportions of the compound (VI) and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde was heated under reflux for about 1 hour. On cooling a crystalline precipitate slowly separated which crystallised from glacial acetic acid in orange rectangular plates, yield 75%. It resinifies at 233-35°. (Found: N, 7.29. $C_{22}H_{14}O_5N_2$ requires N, 7.25 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali.

1-Naphthyl-3:5-cinnamylidene-2:4:6-triketopiperidine (VII, R=PhCH:CH).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the above compound. The product crystallised from a large quantity of glacial acetic acid in bright red rectangular plates, m.p. 263-64° (decomp.) It is insoluble in alkali. (Found: C, 78.19; H, 4.91. $C_{24}H_{17}O_3N$ requires C, 78.47; H, 4.63 per cent).

Ethyl 2:6-dicarbethoxyiminothiopyran-4-one-3:5-dicarboxylate (VI).—Sodium (2.3 g.) was gradually added to a solution of ethyl acetone dicarboxylate (10.2 g.) in absolute ether (200 c.c.). After the evolution of hydrogen had ceased, a toluene solution of carbethoxythiocarbimide (13.5 g., prepared according to the method of Doran, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 69, 326) was added, when the reaction commenced at once with evolution of heat, yielding in a short time a fine yellow solid. After standing overnight, the precipitate was filtered, dissolved in water and acidified when there was evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen. The dark red viscous oil when kept in a vacuum desiccator, slowly changed into a semi-solid mass. It was twice crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (b.p. 75-90°) in beautiful colourless needles, m. p. 122-123°, yield 2.5 g. [Found: N, 6.67; S, 7.82; M. W. (by titration), 434. $C_{17}H_{22}O_9N_2S$ requires N, 6.51; S, 7.44 per cent. M. W., 430). It is soluble in alkali and precipitated by acids, and is not desulphurised by oxide of mercury.

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